

Engage, Improve, Excel

A guide to increase engagement with the evaluation tool

Why does engagement matter?

- **Boost collaboration**
Using the tool brings faculty, students, and administrators together to improve the quality assurance of your education through teamwork.
- **Builds trust & transparency**
Using the tool creates a culture of openness by involving all stakeholders in the process of evaluation.
- **Improves teaching & learning**
Feedback-driven insights from the tool will lead to smarter teaching methods and happier, more successful students.

General tips for engagement

- **Keep everyone in the loop**
Share summarized results through newsletters or meetings to promote transparency and engagement.
- **Turn feedback into action**
Include clear next steps or action plans to show responsiveness and build trust.
- **Celebrate success together**
Acknowledge and celebrate the efforts of faculty and students in improving the process.
- **Highlight real impact**
Share stories of how feedback inspired meaningful changes or innovative solutions.
- **Ask for more feedback**
Conduct mini-surveys to gather ideas on improving the tool and evaluation process.
- **Stay open and accessible**
Maintain a clear line of communication for ongoing suggestions and concerns.

How to get stakeholders engaged?

1 Faculty members

- **Use data to drive growth**
Show how evaluation data can refine teaching methods and boost student outcomes.
- **Highlight career benefits**
Connect feedback to career growth - think teaching portfolios, promotions or awards.
- **Support with workshops**
Host sessions to help faculty interpret and apply the evaluation data.
- **Share easy-to-use guides**
Provide tutorials and resources for understanding and leveraging student feedback.
- **Showcase success stories**
Highlight real examples of faculty improvements learning to better learning experiences.
- **Feature testimonials**
Let faculty share how the tool has transformed their teaching approach.

2 Exchange students

- **Show the impact**
Demonstrate how student feedback leads to real course improvement and better learning experiences.
- **Share success stories**
Highlight examples where past feedback sparked positive changes in teaching or course design.
- **Emphasize confidentiality**
Reassure students that their responses are anonymous and handled with care.
- **Build trust through transparency**
Explain how the data is collected, used and stored to foster trust in the process.
- **Encourage honest feedback**
Create a supportive environment where students feel their opinions truly matter.
- **Use videos or visuals**
Develop guides or visuals showing how their input shapes the evaluation of the courses.

3 International Relations Offices

- **Appoint Ambassadors**
Designate department leads or ambassadors to champion the tool and boost participation.
- **Communicate the value**
Ensure ambassadors regularly highlight how the tool benefits students, faculty, and the exchange program.
- **Facilitate feedback discussions**
Host sessions to review evaluation results and gather input for both faculty and students.
- **Brainstorm actionable solutions**
Collaboratively develop solutions to address key issues revealed by the data.
- **Form interdepartmental committees**
Create workgroups that represent diverse perspectives to turn feedback into action at the university.
- **Offer ongoing support**
Provide training and resources to teachers and faculty to better understand and use the tool in the exchange program.